

FARMERS' PERCEPTION OF MEDIA COVERAGE OF THE INSECURITY IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

Despite Nigeria's rich agricultural soils, good climatic conditions and agricultural diversity, agricultural production have continued to decline in recent times. This is majorly attributed to the heightened insecurity caused by the conflicts between herdsmen and farmers and these conflicts were either under or not covered at all by the media. This poses a major threat to Nigeria and in particular, farmers' food security and income. The main objective of this paper is to ascertain the level of media coverage and farmers' perception of the media coverage of insecurity in Enugu State. Data were collected from 400 farmers using a multistage sampling technique and analysed with descriptive statistics (percentages and frequency counts) and measured with a 4-point Likert-type scale rating. The study identified radio (65%) was the major source of information by the farmers and farmer/herder clashes (4.10), corruption and unethical practices (3.22), pervasive marginalisation or material inequalities (3.12) among others were sequentially ranked from 1 - 7 respectively as the causes of insecurity in the state. A total of 188(51%) farmers reported to have rarely heard about insecurity through the media. They further identified that media houses should among others be apolitical in their reportage (4.32) to curb insecurities in the state. Therefore, media practitioners should be constantly trained to have a balanced and impartial reportage and refrain from any action that portrays any selective treatment in their reportage of the security issues in the country.

Keywords: Agricultural production, Enugu state, farmers, herdsmen, media, insecurity.

Introduction

Nigeria is a country with a total geographical area of 923,768 square kilometres. It has great potential in agricultural production with highly diversified ecological conditions suitable for agricultural diversification. More than 70% of her citizens are engaged in agricultural production (Ajadi, Oladele, Ikegami, & Tsuruta, 2015). The country produces a wide variety of crops, livestock, forestry and fisheries products. Due to the diversified ecological conditions in the country, farming has been sectionalised according to products most suited for a particular area. Agricultural production has declined drastically and this can be attributed to insecurities.

Security is a major target of SDG 16 which aims to promote sustainable development through peaceful and inclusive societies (DCAF, OSCE/ODIHR & UN Women, 2019). Human Security emphasizes a violence-free world where people are safe (UN, 2017). Insecurity can be defined as a breach of peace and

security; whether historical, religious, ethnic, regional, civil, social, economic, and political that contributes to recurring conflicts, and leads to wanton destruction of lives and property. Literally, it could be referred to as an unsafe feeling, a state of mind characterized by self-doubt and vulnerability or just a plain fear of being unsafe in an environment. The state of being secure is very important for national cohesion, peace and sustainable development. It is the foundation for social convention between the citizens and the state; it serves as a fundamental right and prerogative for every citizen in which people willingly surrendered their rights to the government who oversees their survival. This survival depends on the states mechanisms/strategies in place to avoid, prevent, curtail, reduce, or resolve violent conflicts, and threats that originate from states and non-state actors, political, economic and religious factors.

Presently, Nigeria is experiencing political, economic and social insecurity orchestrated by poor leadership, corruption, money laundering, unemployment, underemployment, gender inequality, poverty, illiteracy, religious and ethnic fanaticism. These have led to major security challenges in the country; kidnapping, armed robbery, killings, abductions, terrorism, human trafficking, sexual exploitation, harassment and abuse. The upsurge in banditry, kidnapping and bloodletting across the country is quite frightening. The general insecurity is indeed worrisome with bandits continually wreaking havoc on hapless citizens. Over the years, farmers/herders clash have become a major issue to national security and most of the notable acts of terrorism in Nigeria. This is due to the overlap of interest by the farmers and herders for the control of land resources. This conflict has escalated, taking another dimension of ethnic and religious undertone with little effort from the government to address them. Ethnic jingoists and politicians have been benefitting from these strives and without doubt have succeeded in creating a divide between the farmers and pastoralists, especially in less educated communities.

Perhaps, the growing insecurity in Nigeria has led to the creation of informal security networks in almost all the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria to respond to the seeming failure of the state authorities to guarantee the safety of her people especially the farmers, thus changing the security narratives in the country to self-help. Amotekun created by the governors of the Southwestern states was the first informal zonal security network and followed by Ebube Agu created by the Southeastern states' governors including Enugu state. However, encouraged by the governors' failure to fund and equip the security outfit and the growing insecurity in the zone, Onyendu Mazi Nnamdi Kanu, the supreme leader of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), a proscribed separatist group by the Nigeria state authorities established another informal zonal security network known as Eastern Security Network (ESN) to among other things, defend and safeguard the people of the Southeast geo-political zone against banditry and terrorism.

The speed with which insecurity is growing in Nigeria particularly Enugu state is worrisome. On daily bases, people are psychologically and emotionally bordered for their safety and that of their loved ones. This growing trauma is a result of the unending kidnapping, carnages and the gruesome sights of lifeless/mutilated bodies of loved family members, colleagues, associates and friends' which litter everywhere on the streets and the public sphere (Onah, *et al.*, 2021). The present condition in the state embodies a state of hopelessness, vulnerability and frustration where citizens do not sleep peacefully and farmers no longer farm due to the fear of the notorious bandits, kidnapping, maiming and killings. The unrest in the state has threatened and continues to frustrate the trend for the socio-economic and political growth of the zone. The continuous killings of prominent personnel in Igbo land have brought to question the dexterity of the country's intelligence community in this regard. This is, perhaps, the worst in the annals of the State security history.

In the search for global peace, the mass media is very crucial in promoting development. It uses various communication strategies like news reporting not only to avert violence and strife but to douse insecurity and tension. When the chips are down, the media provides alternative platforms for those aggrieved through insecurity to air their grievances instead of taking to arms. Studies (Ogugua, Idoko & Okoli,

2020) have shown that through adequate, balanced and objective reportage, people who hitherto would have taken to arms to express their displeasure are informed, enlightened and most importantly convinced to seek the option of dialogue or legal redress. However, how the media have played this role in Enugu state has become a subject of interest prompting this study. No doubt, the media have the power to resolve and escalate crises, therefore, evaluating the place of the media in resolving insecurity has become an important subject to the government, researchers and peace and conflict resolution experts. On this basis, this study aims to ascertain the farmers perception of media coverage of insecurity in Enugu State.

Solutions to the Rising Insecurities in Nigeria

Good leadership: The government of President Muhammadu Buhari should rejig the nation's security architecture to tackle the nation's security problems. There should be a new plan of action to rout the menacing bandits and kidnappers. With Nigeria ranking third in the Global Terrorism Index (GTI) (2018), it would be highly regrettable that the modest achievements made by this government in the war against insurgents might be diminished by the raging insecurity across the country. The government should do everything possible to quickly tackle banditry, kidnapping and other security challenges.

Politics: Most times we have seen the challenge of insecurity as failure in governance on the part of a particular ruling party with all efforts being sabotaged by the opposing parties or individuals. Without security, there will be no peace and development. The politicians should eschew their political differences and treat the growing insecurity as a national problem. They should all come together to tackle it. We say this because without security, the nation's nascent democracy will be threatened. Insecurity also threatens foreign investors.

Employment and Poverty alleviation Programmes: As part of measures to tackle the rising lawlessness in the country, the Federal and State governments should frontally address the problem of unemployment and poverty in the country. There is no doubt that unemployment and poverty must have largely contributed to the escalation of the security challenges in the country. Government must strive to save the country from the looming anarchy.

Adequate security measures: The Nigerian Armed Forces and other security agencies should be adequately equipped so that they can tackle the insecurity in the country. The rising insecurity has made the calls for state and community policing more imperative now than ever before. My belief is that the decentralization of the police will go a long way in curbing most of the crimes in the country.

Education: All Nigerian child must have basic education and practical knowledge of some skills.

Strict observance of border surveillance protocol: There should be strict observance of border protocol to prevent illegal entry or exit of individuals without official documentation. This will help prevent both terrorism, human trafficking, money laundering and other crimes.

Restructuring: the genesis of most of the problems in Nigeria is because we avoid dialogue; this would help bring most of the issues such as marginalization and secessionist tendencies to table for a justifiable solution accepted by all to be proffered. There is need to engage the agitators and address the root causes of their many years of marginalization or sense of marginalization.

Punishment of Offenders: Perpetrators of crimes like terrorisms, banditries, kidnapping and killers must be made to face the full wrath of the law. The more they are pardoned; the more others are encouraged to perpetrate crime. Any citizen confirmed to have corruptly enriched him through terrorism, banditry and kidnapping, should not only be made to regurgitate such ill-gotten wealth but should permanently lose all his properties to the federal government.

Finally, individuals, organizations especially the military/para-military, communities and government have important role to play to minimize the rate of crimes and insecurity in Nigeria. The youths must learn to shun all manner of crimes so that the security of the Nigerian citizens will be highly assured. To tolerate crime is to debase the social, economic and political security of all.

Methodology

This study was conducted in Enugu State, Nigeria with a population of about 4,411,119 persons (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2016). The State is geographically situated between latitude 6° 21'N and 6° 33'N, and longitude 7° 25'E and 7° 38'E on the northwestern fringe of southeastern Nigeria. Taro Yamane's method was employed in determining the study's sample size. This is mathematically shown as follows;

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad 1$$

Where N indicates the population size and e is the margin error at a 95% confidence interval (0.05).
Sample size = 4,411,119 / (1 + 4,411,119 (0.05²)) = 399.99 ≈ 400.

The study used a multi-stage sampling procedure. In stage one, five (5) local government areas (LGAs) were chosen namely Igbo-Eze North, Oji-river, Enugu East, Isi-Uzo and Uzo-uwani. This is because of their high rate of agricultural production. The second stage consisted of selecting two (2) towns from each of the LGAs, making a total of ten (10) towns. In the third stage, two (2) villages were chosen at random from each of the towns making a total of twenty (20), and then twenty (20) farmers were randomly chosen from each village, totalling four hundred (400) farmers studied.

A structured questionnaire which passed reliability and validity tests was used to gather data from the sampled audience. Descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency counts, etc was used to ascertain the level of media coverage. The farmers' perception of the media coverage of insecurity in the study area was determined using a 4-point Likert-type rating scale with a mean score of 2.5.

Results and Discussion

Out of the 400 copies of the questionnaire administered, 368 were completed and returned representing a response rate of 92%. The high response rate was a result of the personalization of the distribution. The following are the analyses.

Demographic Data

The results of Table 1 show that the majority (61%) of the farmers studied were females with an average age of 45 years 4 months. This result is in line Onyekuru *et al.*, (2021) and Onyekuru & Apeh (2017) that farming was dominated by female farmers because they were burden with the role of taking care of the family. Their education status is low with only 32 per cent of the farmers being educated and the majority (73%) married. With about 96% of respondents indicating that their main occupation was farming, this may not reflect the ideal situation of the inhabitants of the state because the study only focused on farmers. They had an average farming experience of 14 years and a month and a household size of approximately 4 members. The result further showed that they are mostly (94%) rural inhabitants. Please note that the above percentages for the dummy variables were derived by multiplying the mean value of the individual variables by 100. The results of this study indicate that the farmers were mainly old women who are very vulnerable to physical attacks on the farm.

Table 1: The farmers' demographic data

Descriptive Variables	Description	Mean	SD
Gender	Dummy; male = 1	0.39	0.64
Age	Years	45.4	08.49
Education	Dummy; Educated = 1	0.32	2.25
Marital Status	Dummy; married = 1	0.73	0.58
Occupation	Dummy; Farming = 1	0.96	0.31
Household size	Household members	3.72	1.35
Farming Experience	Years of farming	14.1	6.03
Location	Dummy; rural = 1	0.94	0.52

Sources: Field Survey, 2022; (NB:)

Sources of Media Information

The outcome of Table 2 indicates that the majority (65%) of the farmers received media information through the radio. This shows that radio can perfectly play a vital role in disseminating information to the farmers even in the face of crises to help them with safety information. The result equally shows that radio is a veritable tool for communicating with both the educated and uneducated audience with a few (32%) of the farmers having attained formal education. Print media recorded zero with most of the areas visited inaccessible mostly during the rainy season therefore preventing print media vendors from regular access to disseminate their newspapers.

Table 2: Media Sources print media, social media, television radio

Media Sources	Yes (%) (n = 368)
Print	00
Radio	65
Social	11
Television	24

Sources: Field Survey, 2022

The Farmers' Perception of the Causes of Insecurity in the State

Table 3 depicts the result of the farmers' perception of the causes of insecurity in Enugu state. It showed that having mean scores equal to or above 2.5, seven causes of insecurity were identified and farmer/herder clashes ($\bar{x} = 4.10$) were ranked first. This supports the findings of Enimu, and Isa (2019) that herders/farmers clashes were the most highly perceived insecurity among farmers in Bauchi.

Corruption and unethical practices ($\bar{x} = 3.22$) second, pervasive marginalisation or material inequalities ($\bar{x} = 3.12$) third, poverty/hunger ($\bar{x} = 3.09$) fourth, terrorism ($\bar{x} = 2.64$) fifth, youth unemployment ($\bar{x} = 2.61$) sixth and the struggle for resources and land ($\bar{x} = 2.53$) seventh. The findings confirm the findings of Salimonu and Falusi (2009) that farmers are confronted with insecurity challenges in Nigeria.

Table 3: Knowledge of Insecurities

Causes of insecurity	Mean (\bar{x}) (n = 368)	Rank
Youth unemployment	2.61*	6 th
Poor leadership, Nepotism and Politicization of every national issue	2.03	12 th
Poverty/hunger	3.09*	4 th
Struggle for Resources and land	2.53*	7 th
Farmer/herder clashes	4.10*	1 st
Cattle rustling	1.79	13 th
Illiteracy	2.40	8 th
Religious Differences and Fanaticism	1.09	16 th
Ethnicity	2.11	11 th
Corruption and unethical practices	3.22*	2 nd
Human trafficking	1.60	14 th
Porous borders	2.23	10 th
Terrorism	2.64*	5 th
High/uncontrolled population growth rate	2.39	9 th
Pervasive marginalisation or material Inequalities	3.12*	3 rd
Biafra agitation	1.54	15 th

Sources: Field Survey, 2022; (NB: *Accepted (accept if $\bar{x} \geq 2.5$ and reject if $\bar{x} < 2.5$))

Media Coverage of Insecurity in Enugu state

From Table 4, the majority (51%) of the farmers attested that they rarely hear about insecurity through the media especially the radio that they are very conversant with. This is followed by the 25% who indicated that they occasionally hear about it through the media. This implies that media operators have not lived up to expectations in this regard. Media houses should be steadfast in their reportage, especially during crises to work hard in creating awareness of basic security tips. Despite the very important role placed on

the media by the Constitution of Nigeria, they are yet to rise to be effectively mobilized as a tool for combating insecurity in the country. This may be due to the challenges faced by practitioners ranging from poor welfare packages, lack of continuous and constant training on emerging issues, the tendency of journalists to be self-censored for fear of victimization by their employers or the government to the reluctance of citizens to give information for fear of being attacked.

Table 4: Level of Media Coverage of Insecurity in the State

Media Coverage	Yes (%) (n = 368)
Always	04
Often	08
Occasionally	25
Rarely	51
Can't remember	12

Sources: Field Survey, 2022

Farmers' Perceptions on the Possible Ways Media can curb insecurity in Enugu state

Table 5 shows the farmers' perception of the possible ways media can help in curbing insecurity in Enugu state. The result shows that the farmers perceived that the media can help in curbing insecurity in the state through in-depth, apt and timely reportage of security issues ($\bar{x} = 3.01$), decisive reportage on security issues ($\bar{x} = 2.51$), deliberately designing features/programmes to talk against crimes ($\bar{x} = 4.11$), allotting airtime/space to report/discuss terrorism, kidnapping and other crimes capable of breeding insecurity ($\bar{x} = 3.54$), deliberately designing features/programmes for public enlightenment on security tips ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), by being apolitical in their reportage ($\bar{x} = 4.32$) and exposing crimes ($\bar{x} = 3.97$).

Table 5: Farmers' Perception of media reportage of Insecurity

Farmers' Perceptions on Possible Media Security Reportage	Mean (\bar{x}) (n = 368)	Rank
In-depth, apt and timely in their reportage	3.01*	6 th
Decisive on security issues	2.51*	7 th
Design deliberate features/programmes to talk against crimes	4.11*	2 rd
Allot airtime/space to report/discuss terrorism, kidnapping and other crimes capable of breeding insecurity	3.54*	5 th
Design deliberate features/programmes for public enlightenment on security tips	4.00*	3 rd
Media houses should be apolitical in their reportage	4.32*	1 st
Utilized in exposing crimes	3.97*	4 th

Sources: Field Survey, 2022; (NB: *Accepted (accept if $\bar{x} \geq 2.5$ and reject if $\bar{x} < 2.5$))

Conclusion

This empirical study investigated the farmers' perception of the media coverage of insecurity in Enugu State. The findings showed that the majority of the farmers in the area were old women with little or no education. Their old age makes them physically vulnerable to insecurities on and off the farm. Radio was shown to be the most available source of information by these farmers. The farmer/herder clashes, corruption and unethical practices; pervasive marginalisation or material inequalities, poverty/hunger, terrorism, youth unemployment and the struggle for resources and land were sequentially ranked from 1 – 7 respectively as the farmers perceived causes of insecurity in the state. They further perceived that the media can help curb these security challenges through apt, decisive, in-depth and timely reportage of security issues, by deliberately designing features/programmes to talk against crimes and enlighten the public on security tips, by allotting airtime/space to report/discuss terrorism, kidnapping and other crimes capable of breeding insecurity, by being apolitical in their reportage and exposing crimes without fear. Therefore, we recommend that the media should be impartial in their reportage and refrain from any action that portrays any selective treatment in their reportage of the security issues in the country. The welfare of the practitioners should be improved, they should be constantly trained on emerging issues of security and the citizens should also support this fight by providing reliable information to the practitioners for their reportage.

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